

Collaboration Agreement

Global Search for Regulators of Coral Heat Resilience

Funded by the Paul G. Allen Family Foundation (PGAFF)

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Adapted from the Alaska NSF Epscor Fire and Ice project & the Tara Pacific Ocean Consortium¹

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This document establishes processes and methods to ensure an open and collaborative culture within the Global Search Project. This agreement is a living document. It will be reviewed on a regular basis and adjusted to reflect changing circumstances.

¹ https://zenodo.org/record/3952296#.Yd2X_i-B1yp

Part I. Intention & Collaborative Interaction

Shared respect and collaboration:

The complex nature of our effort and our geographic dispersion necessitates that we operate under a culture of communication, collaboration, and shared respect. We strive to operate in a spirit of curiosity and knowledge sharing to deliver world class research for the betterment of coral reefs and an inclusive learning environment for all.

We will adhere to a code of conduct based on the following principles:

- Respect the laws of the country, region, and traditional custodians of the land and sea where we work
- Display scientific integrity grounded in honesty
- Assume that others have good intentions
- Mentor the next generation of scientists and provide opportunities to grow for all
- Receive and give constructive feedback and respectful discussion to learn from each other and our stakeholders
- Provide opportunities for everyone to have their say and to be heard
- Engage in multidisciplinary research and challenge assumptions/conventions through discussions, analysis, and synthesis
- Build further capacity to grow the goals and objectives of the project
- Represent one another and the project in a professional and positive manner externally, consistent with communication and collaborative agreements

Project Team expectations:

We value the development of a strong, communicative team and the establishment of an inclusive, integrated student cohort.

Participants are expected to:

- Undertake high quality research to meet project objectives
- Participate in leadership and/or science component meetings; if not able to attend individual meetings, they are expected to review actions, notes, and/or video.
- Provide timely information for annual reports, project evaluation, and other ongoing project needs as per expectations/communications.
- Participate in outreach / science communication efforts
- Commit to collecting, curating, sharing with the team and making openly available the highest quality data we can
- Adhere to publication principles of all partner organizations.
- Acknowledge funding support. All papers, presentations, and other intellectual materials produced under the grant must state: “We acknowledge funding by the Paul G. Allen Family Foundation.”

Expectations around timely engagement and feedback include:

- We will make and provide realistic commitments that we keep.
- Urgent matters that cannot be planned are dealt with as needed cognisant of time zones.
- Deadlines explicit and proportional to the level of request. Minimum two and up to six weeks on major tasks
- Early notice of manuscript intent via standing agenda item at team meetings and shared google doc
- Enough time for authors to adhere to institutional protocols around publication. Likely two weeks.
- We will remind each other of deadlines with automated and personal reminders within reason.

Data storage and sharing:

Researchers will comply with all expectations regarding research data imposed by NOAA, PGAFF, RRAP, DFG, and any other co-funding or leveraging organizations as detailed in the Data Management Plan.

These include:

- Adhere to Intellectual Property (IP) arrangements of contracts
- Make research data available for access and reuse via the Global Search data portal and other databases where appropriate (e.g., NCBI, Zenodo, GitHub) and under appropriate safeguards as outlined in Data Management and Communication plans.
- Agree to share data with team members throughout the project
- Adhere to (meta)data standards as per Data Management Plan.
- Maintain data confidentiality in accordance with existing standards and requirements when handling personal information, or personally or community identifiable information.
- It is expected that raw data collected as part of Global Search will be publicly available at 12 months after collection or when published in a peer review journal, whichever comes first.

Part II. Roles & Team

Roles and responsibilities:

The project has three categories of membership:

- **The Leadership team** are the PIs listed on the original proposal (Voolstra, Barshis, Bay, Baums, Baliga, Valenzuela) and a PGAFF representative. Each PI leads a regional team. Valenzuela and Baliga co-lead the systems biology integration.
- **Co-PIs and post-docs** are those that draw a salary from the project .
- **Technicians** collect data and draw salary or are leveraged to deliver the project.
- **Research Students** are those that work on specific/regional components of the project to meet the requirements of a research degree like Honors, Masters, or PhD. Research students collect data with research technicians under the supervision of a PI, Co-PI, or post-doc

The leadership team together with their graduate students, postdocs, and technicians constitute the **Project Team**.

Collaborators are those outside the project team that make a significant contribution to components of the Project on a case by case basis. They include research student co-supervisors.

The **Leadership Team** will be responsible for carrying out the mission of the project, reporting results, managing resources, reviewing plans for manuscripts and presentations, supporting evaluation, managing permits, permissions, and communicating with extended team members and partners. The Leadership team will communicate via email and meet as needed to resolve matters not involving the whole Project team. The Leadership will meet quarterly if needed.

The **Project Team** will meet every month to operationally manage and scientifically collaborate to successfully deliver the project. The regional PIs will meet with their regional teams as often as needed and thematic break-outs may be formed as needed. Meeting chairs will rotate among team leadership members and we commit to a shared responsibility of note keeping and action registers. Meeting chairs will circulate agendas with as much lead time as possible (ie within the preceding week). Operational, technical, and scientific questions will be discussed through presentations and collaboration on live documents to develop a shared understanding of the project among the full project team, including students and stakeholders. Meetings will progress if more than 3 parties are available.

The **Project Team** and **Collaborators** will communicate as needed. A project wide annual meeting will provide an opportunity to celebrate successes, share ideas and results, offer feedback, reflect on past activities and plan future ones.

Part III. Authorship & Publication

Authorship:

Team members agree to adopt a publishing model, which includes the following guiding principles:

- We anticipate that all project outputs will be multi-authored due to the collaborative nature of the research. Outputs include papers, presentations and abstracts, reports, media releases, and web-stories
- Authorship is inclusive (including students and collaborators), but avoids honorary authorships.
- Group members are pro-active about their interest in participating in manuscripts and presentations, and lead authors are open to involvement of others according to co-authorship principles
- Lead Authors communicate early and often about the roles, expectations, and responsibilities of co-authors via project team meetings and publication datasheet in form of a shared google doc
- The Leadership Team (PIs) will contribute to all papers coming out of Global Search unless they indicate otherwise - i.e., opt-out
- Post-docs are opt-out on their regional papers and encouraged opt-in on others
- Research students are opt-out of thesis papers and invited opt-in on others
- Collaborators are invited opt-in generally, but opt-out when co-supervised research student outputs.

For an individual to qualify as a co-author of manuscript, presentation, or other outputs, they must make at least two of the contributions listed below (people who contribute in one category should be noted in the acknowledgments):

- Conceived the idea for the manuscript
- Wrote grants to secure funding to undertake the project
- Designed the experiment
- Supervised project and staff inc budgets and (financial) reporting.
- Performed research, such as data collection, analysis, or modeling
- Contributed new concepts, methods, models or interpretation presented in the manuscript, presentation or other output.
- Drafted figures and table
- Wrote parts of the manuscript
- Performed critical content review.

Authorship position:

For an individual to qualify as the lead author, they must be responsible for the primary analysis and/or presentation of the data and results and/or be the primary author of the majority of text presented. For an individual to qualify as the senior author, they must be the primary supervisor of the lead author or the topic specialist. In cases where more than one individual leads the

analysis and writing, a co-first authorship model may be possible. In the case of multiple individuals substantially contributing to the manuscript (i.e., senior author position), a co-corresponding authorship may be appropriate to recognize their contributions.

Global Search Publications:

We recognise Global Search publications to be those that:

- Report on (i.e., first publication of) data from a large fraction (e.g. >50%) of samples collected from any protocol or from a biogeographic region, or
- Synthesize knowledge on the project topic (review, meta-analyses, opinion).

We will openly disclose and discuss outputs and authorship via established communication pathways (e.g., email and meetings)

Advance notice of publication

Before starting to work on a publication, e.g. a journal article or a dataset, senior authors are asked to consult with the project **leadership team** to assess if the proposed work constitutes a Global Search publication. In case the proposed work constitutes a Global Search publication it will be included in the publication datasheet in the Global Search Google Drive (lead author nominated). and the project **team members** are given the opportunity to listen to a presentation, or read a detailed abstract describing the proposed work. Following this, they can offer to contribute further to the publication to warrant authorship. The project team members are given the opportunity to read the manuscript, at least 14 days before submission, and have 30 days to request being added individually to the list of authors list.

Part IV. Conflict resolution

Conflict resolution:

Team members will strive to be transparent and respectful, to promote civil dialogue and to avoid unhealthy conflict. Despite best intentions, conflicts may occur and we recognize that robust intellectual debate is important for the development and creation of transdisciplinary research. The **project team** agrees to ensure that scientific debate and matters of other concern are raised and dealt with in a respectful manner; that everyone is given an opportunity to speak and to be heard; to assist team members in resolving conflict through additional conversation and conflict resolution; and to maintain an open and civil dialogue in all interactions. In the event that a team members are not adhering to these standards they are encouraged to share their concerns with **leadership team** personnel who will serve as peer mediators and help to craft a sustainable resolution.

Conflicts of Interest:

We follow the National Academy of Sciences and also note that "a conflict of interest in research exists when the individual has interests in the outcome of the research that may lead to a personal advantage and that might therefore, in actuality or appearance, compromise the integrity of the research". Team members will identify and address potential conflicts of interest through the appropriate Office of Research Integrity within their respective organizations. Leadership team will discuss and try to resolve issues in case of conflict.

Part V. Misc

Communications/Publicity:

A communication plan will be developed and approved by all project partners.

Grantee agrees to acknowledge support from The Paul G. Allen Family Foundation in all of Grantee's materials related to the Project, in a manner to be approved in writing by the Foundation (email approval acceptable). For design, collateral, advertising, or other publishing needs, Grantee should request publication-ready and electronic art.

For any press release related to the Project, Grantee agrees to include an approved paragraph about The Paul G. Allen Family Foundation, and the name and number of an approved media contact from The Paul G. Allen Family Foundation.

For all press releases, marketing, or social media promotion, Grantee will provide at least two business days written notice by email prior to publication, a final draft of the proposed press release, including the date and time by which approval is requested (email approval acceptable). Grantee agrees to incorporate Foundation's requested changes to the portion of any press release that mentions Paul G. Allen, Jody Allen, The Paul G. Allen Family Foundation, or quotes any personnel.

Logos and content requests as well as any written materials submitted for approval to the Foundation pursuant to this Section should be submitted to press@vulcan.com. Questions can be directed to Grants and Contract Manager at (206) 342-2000.

The Paul G. Allen Family Foundation and its affiliates may include references to Grantee's organization, in relation to this grant, among sample grantees including, in social media and on its website and those of its affiliates, including Vulcan.com. Grantee agrees to provide electronic or printed copy of Grantee's logo, as well as photographs of the Project to use for such purpose.

Leverage of samples/ data / field resources for other projects and funding applications:

- Leverage of GS samples/data/field resources for attracting additional funding is encouraged.
- Regular discussion amongst the leadership team about associated projects/proposals/etc. is expected to avoid potential conflicts/competition.
- When resources are region-specific, then the expectation is of notice but not necessarily inclusion.